

Original article

Neonatal outcomes in obstetric fistula-associated pregnancies at the Nigerian northeast regional fistula centre

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Abstract

Background: Obstetric fistula is a severe childbirth complication that disproportionately affects women in resource-limited settings. It has significant yet understated impacts on neonatal outcomes. Given the high burden of obstetric fistula in Northeastern Nigeria, investigating neonatal outcomes in this region is critical. This study aimed to evaluate neonatal outcomes in pregnancies complicated by obstetric fistula and to assess the associations between maternal demographic and obstetric factors and neonatal outcomes among women managed for Obstetric fistula at the National Obstetric Fistula Centre in Bauchi, Nigeria. **Materials and Methods:** This study utilised a retrospective sample of 400 women managed at the National Obstetric Fistula Centre in Bauchi from January 1, 2019, to December 31, 2024. IBM SPSS version 23 was used for data analysis, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$. **Results:** The mean maternal age was 28.35 ± 9.22 years, with a median age of 25.0 years, and the mean parity was 3.98 ± 3.34 . The prevalence of stillbirth was 74.0%, 20.5% of the neonates were alive at the time of maternal discharge following repair, and the prevalence of early neonatal death was 5.5%. Maternal age showed no statistically significant association with neonatal outcomes ($p = 0.68$), whereas the place of delivery was significantly associated with neonatal outcomes ($p = 0.003$). **Conclusion:** The observed neonatal outcomes are in line with regional trends. A significant correlation existed between delivery location and neonatal outcomes, underscoring the importance of strengthening healthcare systems for mothers and newborns in this setting.

Keywords: Neonatal outcome, Obstetric fistula, Stillbirth.

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ISSN: Print; 2992-555X Electronic: 3092-9865
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20667627>

Date Submitted: 20th February 2026
Date Accepted: 18th March 2026
Date Published Online: 10th May 2026

Cite this article as: Iragbogie A. Imoudu, Halima Mukaddas, Olarenwaju E. Ogbara, Muhammad I. Faruk. Neonatal outcomes in obstetric fistula-associated pregnancies at the Nigerian northeast regional fistula centre. *The Scholar J Health Scie* 2026; 2 (1): 122-126.

Introduction

Obstetric fistula (OF) is a dreaded childbirth complication, a harsh testament to the inequities in the global healthcare system. It disparately affects women in resource-limited settings with restricted access to emergency obstetric care.¹ The maternal morbidities associated with OF, including secondary infections, psychological trauma, as well as physical and social isolation, are well-documented.²⁻⁴ However, the condition's impact on newborn outcome remains underrecognised. Prolonged obstructed labour, a common cause of OF, increases the risk of fetal morbidities, perinatal asphyxia, birth trauma, sepsis, and neonatal death.⁵⁻⁸ In some studies, the stillbirth rate of OF exceeds 90%, with surviving infants facing high morbidity.⁹⁻¹¹ Nigeria accounts for about 40% of the global burden of OF.¹² The Northeastern region is affected to a greater degree due to multiple factors, including a high poverty rate, low literacy levels, poor access to obstetric services, and high levels of teenage marriages.¹³

The National Obstetric Fistula Centre (NOFIC), Ningi, Bauchi, is the major referral centre for of management in this region. Even though NOFIC Bauchi was established to prioritise care for women with OF, understanding neonatal outcomes is critical as it will strengthen counselling for high-risk pregnancies, emphasise of prevention, and advocate for integrated newborn care in treatment programmes. Moreover, global and regional data on neonatal outcomes of pregnancies complicated by OF are limited. This study fills this gap by studying neonates born to mothers managed for OF at NOFIC Bauchi. The specific objectives of the study include determining the spectrum of neonatal outcomes in pregnancies complicated by OF, determining the prevalence of Stillbirth and Early Neonatal Deaths among neonates delivered from pregnancies complicated by OF during the study period, as well as evaluating the relationships between selected maternal demographic and obstetric factors and neonatal outcomes in pregnancies complicated by of at NOFIC Bauchi.

Materials and methods

Study Design

This was a cross-sectional retrospective study designed to analyse the medical records of women managed for OF at NOFIC Ningi, Bauchi, from January 1, 2019, to December 31, 2024.

Ethical consideration

Approval was acquired from the institution's Health Research Ethics Committee (HREC) before commencement of the study.

Study Population

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Women diagnosed with OF who received treatment at NOFIC Bauchi within the study period.
2. Women with documented obstetric history and treatment outcomes.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Women with incomplete or missing medical records.
2. Women with documented congenital urogenital anomalies unrelated to obstetric fistula.
3. Women who had non-pregnancy-related fistula.

Sampling and Data Collection

The sample size was computed with Yamane's formula: ¹⁴

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$$

Where: n= minimum sample size

N = total population

e = margin of error, 5% with a confidence level of 95%

$$n = \frac{2095}{1 + 2095(0.05^2)} \quad n = 335.9$$

However, four hundred (400) patient records were selected from the 2,095 cases managed within the period under review using systematic sampling.

Health Information personnel retrieved these records, and the authors and an assistant then extracted data from eligible cases using a pre-designed data collection form. Collected data included: maternal age, marital status, education, occupation, residence, parity, Antenatal care attendance, delivery site, delivery mode, cause of OF, gestational age at delivery, neonatal outcome, OF repair status, and maternal mortality status. There was no case of missing data in the selected records.

Data analysis

The collected data were entered into IBM SPSS version 23. Continuous variables were summarised using mean and standard deviation, while categorical data were expressed in proportions. Prevalences were presented in percentages. The Chi-square test was used to assess associations between maternal factors and neonatal outcomes, while Fisher's exact test was used when the expected cell count was less than 5. Results were presented in prose, tables, and a figure; $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results

Records of 400 women were analysed. The mean age was 28.35 ± 9.22 years, with a median age of 25.0 years, while the mean parity was 3.98 ± 3.34 . Four hundred (100.0%) of the participants delivered at term, and had OF repair, and there were no Maternal deaths at NOFIC Bauchi in this cohort. Table 1 summarises the general characteristics of the study participants. Table 2 demonstrates the impact of selected maternal demographic and obstetric features on neonatal outcomes. It shows a statistically significant relationship between the place of delivery and neonatal outcome.

Figure 1 shows the neonatal outcome of this cohort. The prevalence of stillbirth was 74.0%, 20.5% were Alive at the time the mother was discharged post-repair, and the prevalence of Early Neonatal Death was 5.5%.

Table 1. General characteristics of study participants

Characteristics	Frequency (n = 400)	Percentage
Age (years)		
< 18	26	6.5
18-25	186	46.5
26-35	114	28.5
36-45	58	14.5
>45	16	4.0
Marital status		
Married	326	81.5
Single	4	1.0
Divorced	44	11.0
Widowed	26	6.5
Academic background		
No formal education	298	74.5
Primary	48	12.0
Secondary	44	11.0
Tertiary	10	2.5
Occupation		
Full time housewife	312	78.0
Petty trading	14	3.5
Farming	2	0.5
Unemployed	72	18.0
Residence		
Rural	326	81.5
Urban	74	18.5
Parity		
1-3	224	56.0
4-6	82	20.5
7-10	68	17.0
>10	26	6.5
Antenatal attendance		
At least one visit	124	31.0
No visit	276	69.0
Mode of delivery		
Vaginal	194	48.5
Assisted vaginal (forceps)	8	2
Caesarean section	198	49.5
Cause of Obstetric fistula		
Prolonged-obstructed labour	308	77.0
Surgical injury	50	12.5
Forceps	4	1
Unknown	38	9.5
Associated maternal morbidities		
Anaemia	24	6.0
Puerperal sepsis	12	3.0

Discussion

This study examined the neonatal outcomes of pregnancies complicated by OF at NOFIC Bauchi. Findings indicated high Stillbirth and Early Neonatal Death rates, with about a fifth of the

babies living beyond the first 7 days of life. Additionally, neonatal outcomes were significantly influenced by the place of delivery among the women in this study.

Findings from multiple studies, including the current one, demonstrate that the spectrum of neonatal outcomes in pregnancies complicated by OF ranges from stillbirths, early neonatal deaths, to a small proportion of surviving newborns. Overall, the neonatal outcome indicators remain consistently poor across studies.^{7,11,15,16} Ngongo et al conducted a multicentre study in 82 facilities (n=4396 women) in 9 Central and Eastern African countries.

The investigators found a stillbirth prevalence of 84.1%, and 15.9% of the infants were alive at the time of assessment.¹⁶ Similarly, Ayenew found a stillbirth prevalence rate of about 38% among Ethiopian women.⁷ In another large study conducted in Jos, North Central Nigeria, a high stillbirth prevalence of 91.7% was reported, while live births and early Neonatal deaths accounted for 8.3% and 1.6% respectively. The study included 899 OF patients, mostly from the neighbouring states and parts of the Republic of Niger.¹¹

The findings in the present study align with these trends, although with a comparatively lower stillbirth prevalence and higher neonatal survival. These differences may be ascribed to the disparities in maternal characteristics, such as higher mean age and parity, better obstetric care, and the recency of the data in the current study. Notably, the Ethiopian study, which reported the lowest stillbirth rate, was a systematic review and meta-analysis, whereas the other studies utilised a retrospective design.

Previous research has shown that maternal demographic and obstetric characteristics, such as age, academic background, prolonged obstructed labour, and mode of delivery, significantly impacted neonatal outcomes in pregnancies complicated by OF.^{15,17,18} In contrast, we did not detect statistically significant associations for these variables in our study. This speculatively may reflect differences in study populations, contextual settings, and methodological designs. In particular, Muleta et al. conducted a large retrospective analysis involving 14,928 women in Ethiopia; Okot et al. utilised a prospective cohort design with 265 participants; and Korn et al. adopted a mixed-methods approach among 302 post-repair patients in Uganda.

The present study has outlined the range of neonatal outcomes observed at NOFIC Bauchi, including the prevalence of stillbirths and early neonatal deaths. It further identified a significant

Table 2. The impact of selected maternal demographic and obstetric features on neonatal outcome.

Maternal features	Neonatal outcomes			X ²	p-value
	Alive (%)	Stillbirths (%)			
Age (years)				5.68	0.68
< 18	4.0 (15.4)	22.0 (84.6)	0.0 (0.0)		
18-25	42.0 (22.6)	130.0 (69.9)	14.0 (7.5)		
26-35	22.0 (19.3)	88.0 (77.2)	4.0 (3.5)		
36-45	14.0 (24.1)	42.0 (72.4)	2.0 (3.4)		
>45	0.0 (0.0)	14.0 (87.5)	2.0 (12.5)		
Place of delivery				11.76	0.003
Home	24.0 (44.4)	26.0 (48.1)	4.0 (7.4)		
Health facility	58.0 (16.8)	270.0 (78.0)	18.0 (5.2)		
Cause of Obstetric Fistula				8.42	0.21
Prolonged-obstructed labour	56.0 (18.2)	232.0 (75.3)	20.0 (6.5)		
Surgical injury	10.0 (20.0)	40.0 (80.0)	0.0 (0.0)		
Forceps injury	0.0 (0.0)	4.0 (100.0)	0.0 (0.0)		
Unknown	16.0 (42.1)	20.0 (52.6)	2.0 (5.3)		
Parity				8.9	0.35
1-3	46.0 (20.5)	164.0 (73.2)	14.0 (6.3)		
4-6	18.0 (22.0)	62.0 (75.6)	2.0 (2.4)		
7-10	12.0 (17.6)	52.0 (76.5)	4.0 (5.9)		
>10	6.0 (23.1)	18.0 (69.2)	2.0 (7.7)		
Mode of delivery				4.68	0.35
Vaginal	48.0 (24.7)	132.0 (68.1)	14.0 (7.2)		
Assisted vaginal (forceps)	0.0 (0.0)	8.0 (100.0)	0.0 (0.0)		
Caesarean section	34.0 (17.2)	156 (78.8)	8.0 (4.0)		

association between place of delivery and neonatal outcomes, indicating that adverse neonatal outcomes were more common among women who delivered at home. These findings emphasise the dual priority of preventing the occurrence of OF and reducing its associated neonatal morbidity and mortality. They also underscore the urgent need to strengthen maternal and newborn healthcare systems through enhanced antenatal education, improved access to optimal obstetric and newborn care, and the establishment of efficient referral pathways for cases of prolonged obstructed labour. The current study would provide context-specific insights from a high-burden hospital in Northeastern Nigeria, addressing a knowledge gap in OF research. Although the retrospective design limited data accuracy and completeness, the findings provide a foundation for hypothesis generation and inform future prospective or interventional studies aimed at improving maternal and neonatal outcomes in similar settings.

Conclusion

Neonatal outcomes observed at NOFIC Bauchi are consistent with findings reported across other regions of sub-Saharan Africa. However, a significant association was identified between the place of delivery and neonatal outcomes within this

cohort. These findings underline the need to strengthen the maternal and neonatal healthcare system.

Funding

No funding was received for this study.

Authors' Contributions

Iragbogie A. Imoudu conceptualised the study, designed it, and contributed to data collection. He analysed and interpreted the data and drafted the manuscript. Halima Mukaddas was involved in study design, data collection and entry. Olarenwaju E. Ogbara and Muhammad I. Faruk were involved in study design, data collection, and entry. All the authors approved the final draft of the manuscript.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest involved in this research.

Acknowledgement

We thank the Health Information Management unit staff at NOFIC Ningi, Bauchi state, particularly Sanusi Ayuba, for assisting with patient record retrieval. We also acknowledge Nurse Fatima Abubakar's contribution to data collection.

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